

Impact of Urine Blood on Chocolate Likeliness

Shahzadi Tuba*, Muneeba Razzaq, Warisha Amjad, Syed Bilal Hussain & Muhammad Imran Qadir

Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.
Corresponding Author (Shahzadi Tuba) - shahzadituba4@gmail.com*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46759/IIJSR.2022.6406>

Copyright © 2022 Shahzadi Tuba et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 09 November 2022

Article Accepted: 21 December 2022

Article Published: 30 December 2022

ABSTRACT

This study relates the relation between blood in urine and chocolate depicted. Hematuria is a condition in which blood release from body with urine. When we see blood in our urine this condition called gross hematuria and when we can't see the blood in urine with our naked eye it is known as microscopic hematuria. Their more risk factors are age, infection, family history. Main symptoms of this disease are nausea, vomiting, fever, chill and pain in abdomen or back. Chocolate is famous due to its delicious taste and attractive brown color. Chocolate is made up of different types of method in every country. The simplest method of chocolate manufacturing is mixture of sugar, milk and cocoa powder. 60% males have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted. while 53.75% females have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted.

Keywords: Blood in urine; Chocolate depicted; Gross hematuria; Microscopic hematuria; Chemicals.

INTRODUCTION

Hematuria is a condition in which blood release from body with urine. It may be visible or can't see with naked eye. When we see blood in our urine this condition called gross hematuria and when we can't see the blood in urine with our naked eye it is known as microscopic hematuria. The main causes of blood urine is infection in urinary track, infection in kidney, stone in bladder or kidney, cancer and excess working. Their more risk factors are age, infection, family history. Main symptoms of this disease are nausea, vomiting, fever, chill and pain in abdomen or back. To avoid these kind of diseases we have to drink excess water and take less salts, apply good hygiene habits and to prevent bladder cancer avoid smoking and stay away from chemicals. We can easily tested hematuria by blood test, CT scan and kidney biopsy. The blood in urine is a dangerous for the peoples of all ages because it shows symptoms of a serious disease. Some drugs also cause urinary bleeding such as anti-cancer tablets (cyclophosphamide) and penicillin. The blood in urine is also due to tough exercise because the exercise cause dehydration in body and due to dehydration the blood cells break and comes out through urinary tract. In old age the prostate gland becomes enlarged and cause hematuria. The blood in urinary tract is known as hematuria. The blood in urine also comes due to the kidney infections. The blood in urine is very dangerous if you see the blood in urine then urgently consult with your doctor.

In history, the chocolate is first discovered by Mexico in 1900 with the proof of chocolate beverages. It is in different forms i.e liquid solid or also in the form of paste. It is also in the form of cocoa powder which is used in cakes. Different companies prepare different types of chocolate flavors. Chocolate is famous due to its delicious taste and attractive brown color. Chocolate is made up of different types of method in every country. The simplest method of chocolate manufacturing is mixture of sugar, milk and cocoa powder.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

100 contributors of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan participate in this process.

HEMATURIA

If you noted that your urine contains blood then you have to check hematuria by CT scan and MRI. Cystoscopy is another method in which tiny camera attaches with a thread and passed to the bladder to examine the infection in urethra. We collect a urine sample from the patient and after collecting the sample in the tube place it carefully. To examine the blood in urine special type of strips are used. These strips are called dipsticks. We dip the strips into the sample and after sometime red or brown color appears. Sometimes the clots are also present in the blood sample.

STUDY OBJECTIVE

This study explains the link between hematuria and are chocolate depicted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study total 20% males have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted. 60% males have no blood in urine and are chocolate depicted. 0% males have blood in urine and it don't are chocolate depicted. 20% males have no blood in urine and don't are chocolate depicted. Total 8% females have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted. 53.75% females have no blood in urine and are chocolate depicted. 4.25% females have blood in urine and it don't shows are chocolate depicted. 34% females have no blood in urine and don't are chocolate depicted.

Table 1. Link between hematuria and perfume allergy

Gender	Chocolate depicted		Not - chocolate depicted	
	Blood in urine	No blood in urine	Blood in urine	No blood in urine
Male	20%	60%	0%	20%
Female	8%	53.75%	4.25%	34%

CONCLUSION

20% males have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted.while 8% females have blood in urine and are chocolate depicted.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

References

- [1] Qadir MI, Malik SA (2010). Comparison of alterations in red blood cell count and alterations in hemoglobin concentration in patients suffering from rectal carcinoma undergoing 5-fluorouracil and folic acid therapy. *Pharmacologyonline*, N1 3: 240-243.
- [2] Qadir MI, Noor A (2018). *Anemias. Rare & Uncommon Diseases*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. Newcastle, England. ISBN: 978-1-5275-1807-0.
- [3] Qadir MI, Javid A (2018). Awareness about Crohn's Disease in biotechnology students. *Glo Adv Res J Med Medical Sci*, 7(3): 062-064.
- [4] Qadir MI, Saleem A (2018). Awareness about ischemic heart disease in university biotechnology students. *Glo Adv Res J Med Medical Sci*, 7(3): 059-061.
- [5] Qadir MI, Ishfaq S (2018). Awareness about hypertension in biology students. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 08-10.
- [6] Qadir MI, Mehwish (2018). Awareness about psoriasis disease. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 17-18.
- [7] Qadir MI, Shahzad R (2018). Awareness about obesity in postgraduate students of biotechnology. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 14-16.
- [8] Qadir MI, Rizvi M (2018). Awareness about thalassemia in post graduate students. *MOJ Lymphology & Phlebology*, 2(1): 14-16.
- [9] Qadir MI, Ghalia BA (2018). Awareness survey about colorectal cancer in students of M. Phil Biotechnology at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. *Nov Appro in Can Study*, 1(3): NACS.000514.2018.
- [10] Qadir MI, Saba G (2018). Awareness about intestinal cancer in university student. *Nov Appro in Can Study*, 1(3): NACS.000515.2018.